

Kepler Bahhatti and Modified Kepler Bahhatti Indices

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 18 June 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: V.R.Kulli</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Kepler Bahhatti index, modified Kepler Bahhatti index, graph, dendrimer.</p>	<p>We introduce a novel vertex degree based topological index, called Kepler Bahhatti index. Also we put forward the modified Kepler Bahhatti index of a graph. We propose the Kepler Bahhatti and modified Kepler Bahhatti exponentials of a graph. In this study, we determine the newly defined the Kepler Bahhatti indices and their corresponding exponentials for certain dendrimers. Furthermore, we establish some properties of the Kepler Bahhatti index.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Let G be a finite, simple, connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree d_u of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . We refer [1] for undefined notations and terminologies.

A graph index is a numerical parameter mathematically derived from the graph structure. Several graph indices have been considered in Theoretical Chemistry and many graph indices were defined by using vertex degree concept [2]. The Zagreb, Bahhatti, Revan, Gourava indices are the most degree based graph indices in Chemical Graph Theory. Graph indices have their applications in various disciplines in Science and Technology [3, 4, 5].

In applications, Zagreb indices are among the best applications to recognize the physical properties. The first Zagreb index $M_1(G)$ and the second Zagreb index $M_2(G)$ were introduced by Gutman et al. in [6, 7]. They are defined as

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} d_u^2$$

$$M_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} d_u d_v$$

The reciprocal Randic index was introduced in [8, 9] and it is defined as

$$RR(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_u d_v}$$

The Kepler expression was proposed in [10, 11]

$$\pi(r_1 + r_2)$$

$$\text{where } r_1 = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}, \quad r_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a + b),$$

$$a = d_u, b = d_v, a \geq b.$$

The Kepler expression motivates us to introduce a new index, defined as

$$KB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}]$$

which we propose to be named as Kepler Bahhatti index.

Considering the Kepler Bahhatti index, we introduce the Kepler Bahhatti exponential of a graph G and defined it as

$$KB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}}$$

We define the modified Kepler Bahhatti index of a graph G as

$${}^m KB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}}$$

Considering the modified Kepler Bahhatti index, we introduce the modified Kepler Bahhatti exponential of a graph G and defined it as

$${}^m KB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{x^{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}}}$$

Recently, some graph indices were studied in [12, 13, 14, 15, 16].

2. MATHEMATICAL PROPERTIES

Proposition1. Let P be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$KB(P) = 8\sqrt{2}n + 6\sqrt{5} - 24\sqrt{2}.$$

Proof: Let P be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. We obtain two partitions of the edge set of P as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_u=1, d_v=2\}, |E_1| = 2.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_u = d_v=2\}, |E_2| = n - 3.$$

$$KB(P) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}]$$

$$= 2(1+2)\sqrt{1^2 + 2^2} + (n-3)(2+2)\sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}$$

$$= 8\sqrt{2}n + 6\sqrt{5} - 24\sqrt{2}.$$

Proposition2. Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices, m edges and $r \geq 2$. Then

$$KB(G) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) nr^2.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices, $r \geq 2$ and $m = \frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Every edge of G is incident with r edges.

Thus

$$KB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(r+r) + \sqrt{r^2 + r^2}]$$

$$= (2 + \sqrt{2}) rm$$

$$= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) nr^2$$

Corollary 2.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$KB(C_n) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) 4n.$$

Corollary 2.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$KB(K_n) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) n(n-1)^2.$$

Theorem 1. Let G be a simple connected graph. Then

$$KB(G) \geq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) M_1(G)$$

with equality if G is regular.

Proof: By the Jensen inequality, for a concave function $f(x)$,

$$f\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right) \geq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i)$$

with equality for a strict concave function if $x_1 = x_2 = \dots = x_n$. Choosing $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$, we obtain

$$\sqrt{\frac{d_u^2 + d_v^2}{2}} \geq \frac{(d_u + d_v)}{2}$$

thus

$$[(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}] \geq (d_u + d_v) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(d_u + d_v).$$

Hence

$$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}]$$

$$\geq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v).$$

Thus

$$KB(G) \geq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) M_1(G)$$

with equality if G is regular.

Theorem 2. Let G be a simple connected graph. Then

$$KB(G) \leq (1 + \sqrt{2}) M_1(G) - \sqrt{2} RR(G).$$

Proof: It is known that for $1 \leq x \leq y$,

$$f(x, y) = (x + y - \sqrt{xy}) - \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2}}$$

is decreasing for each y . Thus $f(x, y) \geq f(y, y) = 0$.

Hence

$$x + y - \sqrt{xy} \geq \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2}}$$

or
$$\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2}} \leq x + y - \sqrt{xy}.$$

Put $x = d_u$ and $y = d_v$, we get

$$\sqrt{\frac{d_u^2 + d_v^2}{2}} \leq (d_u + d_v) - \sqrt{d_u d_v}$$

or
$$\sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2} \leq \sqrt{2}[(d_u + d_v) - \sqrt{d_u d_v}].$$

Thus
$$(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2} \leq (d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{2}[(d_u + d_v) - \sqrt{d_u d_v}]$$

which implies

$$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}$$

$$\leq (1 + \sqrt{2}) \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v) - \sqrt{2} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_u d_v}.$$

Thus

$$KB(G) \leq (1 + \sqrt{2}) M_1(G) - \sqrt{2} RR(G).$$

Theorem 3. Let G be a simple connected graph. Then

$$KB(G) < 2M_1(G).$$

Proof: It is known that for $1 \leq x \leq y$,

$$\sqrt{x^2 + y^2} < x + y$$

$$(x + y) + \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} < 2(x + y)$$

Setting $x = d_u$ and $y = d_v$, we get

$$(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2} < 2(d_u + d_v).$$

Thus

$$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}] < 2 \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v).$$

Hence $KB(G) < 2M_1(G).$

3. RESULTS FOR DENDRIMER NANOSTARS $D_1[n]$

In this section, we consider a family of dendrimer nanostars with n growth stages, denoted by $D_1[n]$, where $n \geq 0$. The molecular graph of $D_1[4]$ with 4 growth stages is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The molecular graph of $D_1[4]$.

Let G be the molecular graph of dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$. From Figure 1, it is easy to see that the vertices of dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$ are either of degree 1, 2 or 3. We obtain that G has $2^{n+4} - 9$ vertices and $18 \times 2^n - 11$ edges. Also by calculation, we partition the edge set $E(D_1[n])$ into three sets as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_u = 1, d_v = 3\}, \quad |E_1| = 1.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_u = d_v = 2\}, \quad |E_2| = 6 \times 2^n - 2.$$

$$E_3 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_u = 2, d_v = 3\}, \quad |E_3| = 12 \times 2^n - 10.$$

Theorem 4. The Kepler Bhatti index of a dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$ is given by

$$KB(G) = (84 + 12\sqrt{2} + 12\sqrt{13})2^n - 54 + \sqrt{10} + 4\sqrt{2} - 10\sqrt{13}.$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} KB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}] \\ &= 1[(1+3) + \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}] \\ &\quad + (6 \times 2^n - 2)[(2+2) + \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}] \\ &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 10)[(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}] \\ &= (84 + 12\sqrt{2} + 12\sqrt{13})2^n - 54 + \sqrt{10} + 4\sqrt{2} - 10\sqrt{13}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5. The Kepler Bhatti exponential of a dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$ is given by

$$KB(G, x) = 1x^{4+\sqrt{10}} + (6 \times 2^n - 2)x^{4+2\sqrt{2}} + (12 \times 2^n - 10)x^{5+\sqrt{13}}.$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} KB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}} \\ &= 1x^{(1+3) + \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}} + (6 \times 2^n - 2)x^{(2+2) + \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}} \\ &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 10)x^{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}} \\ &= 1x^{4+\sqrt{10}} + (6 \times 2^n - 2)x^{4+2\sqrt{2}} + (12 \times 2^n - 10)x^{5+\sqrt{13}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. The modified Kepler Bhatti index of a dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$ is

$${}^m KB(G) = \frac{1}{4 + \sqrt{10}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n - 2}{4 + 2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{12 \times 2^n - 10}{5 + \sqrt{13}}.$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m KB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{(1+3) + \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n - 2}{(2+2) + \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}} + \frac{12 \times 2^n - 10}{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{4 + \sqrt{10}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n - 2}{4 + 2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{12 \times 2^n - 10}{5 + \sqrt{13}}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 7. The modified Kepler Bhanhatti exponential of a dendrimer nanostar $D_1[n]$ is given by

$${}^m KB(G, x) = 1x^{\frac{1}{4+\sqrt{10}}} + (6 \cdot 2^n - 2)x^{\frac{1}{4+2\sqrt{2}}} + (12 \cdot 2^n - 10)x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m KB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{x^{(d_u+d_v)+\sqrt{d_u^2+d_v^2}}} \\ &= 1x^{\frac{1}{(1+3)+\sqrt{1^2+3^2}}} + (6 \times 2^n - 2)x^{\frac{1}{(2+2)+\sqrt{2^2+2^2}}} \\ &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 10)x^{\frac{1}{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}}} \\ &= 1x^{\frac{1}{4+\sqrt{10}}} + (6 \times 2^n - 2)x^{\frac{1}{4+2\sqrt{2}}} + (12 \times 2^n - 10)x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}} \end{aligned}$$

4. RESULTS FOR DENDRIMER NANOSTARS $D_3[n]$

In this section, we consider of dendrimer nanostars with n growth stages, denoted by $D_3[n]$, where $n \geq 0$. The molecular structure of $D_3[n]$ with 3 growth stages is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The molecular structure of $D_3[3]$

Let G be the graph of a dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$. From Figure 2, it is easy to see that the vertices of dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$ are either of degree 1, 2 or 3. By algebraic method, we obtain that G has $24 \times 2^n - 20$ vertices and $24 \times 2^{n+1} - 24$ edges. Also by algebraic method, we obtain that the edge set $E(D_3[n])$ can be divided into four partitions:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u) = 1, d_G(v) = 3\} & |E_1| &= 3 \times 2^n \\ E_2 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u) = d_G(v) = 2\} & |E_2| &= 12 \times 2^n - 6 \\ E_3 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u) = 2, d_G(v) = 3\} & |E_3| &= 24 \times 2^n - 12 \\ E_4 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u) = d_G(v) = 3\} & |E_4| &= 9 \times 2^n - 6 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 8. The Kepler Bhanhatti index of a dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$ is given by

$$KB(G) = (12\sqrt{10} + 114\sqrt{2} + 72\sqrt{5})2^n - 60\sqrt{2} - 36\sqrt{5}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} KB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n [(1+3) + \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}] \\ &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 6) [(2+2) + \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}] \\ &\quad + (24 \times 2^n - 12) [(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}] \\ &\quad + (9 \times 2^n - 6) [(3+3) + \sqrt{3^2 + 3^2}] \\ &= (12\sqrt{10} + 114\sqrt{2} + 72\sqrt{5})2^n - 60\sqrt{2} - 36\sqrt{5} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 9. The Kepler Bhanhatti exponential of a dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$ is given by

$$KB(G, x) = 3 \cdot 2^n x^{4+\sqrt{10}} + (12 \cdot 2^n - 6)x^{4+2\sqrt{2}} + (24 \cdot 2^n - 12)x^{5+\sqrt{13}} + (9 \cdot 2^n - 6)x^{6+3\sqrt{2}}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} KB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(d_u+d_v)+\sqrt{d_u^2+d_v^2}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{(1+3)+\sqrt{1^2+3^2}} + (12 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(2+2)+\sqrt{2^2+2^2}} \\ &\quad + (24 \times 2^n - 12)x^{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(3+3)+\sqrt{3^2+3^2}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{4+\sqrt{10}} + (12 \times 2^n - 6)x^{4+2\sqrt{2}} \\ &\quad + (24 \times 2^n - 12)x^{5+\sqrt{13}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{6+3\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 10. The modified Kepler Bhanhatti index of a dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$ is

$${}^m KB(G) = \frac{3 \cdot 2^n}{4 + \sqrt{10}} + \frac{12 \cdot 2^n - 6}{4 + 2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{24 \cdot 2^n - 12}{5 + \sqrt{13}} + \frac{9 \cdot 2^n - 6}{6 + 3\sqrt{2}}$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m KB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(d_u + d_v) + \sqrt{d_u^2 + d_v^2}} \\ &= \frac{3 \times 2^n}{(1+3) + \sqrt{1^2 + 3^2}} + \frac{12 \times 2^n - 6}{(2+2) + \sqrt{2^2 + 2^2}} \\ &\quad + \frac{24 \times 2^n - 12}{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}} + \frac{9 \times 2^n - 6}{(3+3) + \sqrt{3^2 + 3^2}} \\ &= \frac{3 \times 2^n}{4 + \sqrt{10}} + \frac{12 \times 2^n - 6}{4 + 2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{24 \times 2^n - 12}{5 + \sqrt{13}} + \frac{9 \times 2^n - 6}{6 + 3\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 11. The modified Kepler Bhanhatti exponential of a dendrimer nanostar $D_3[n]$ is given by

$${}^m KB(G, x) = 3 \cdot 2^n x^{\frac{1}{4+\sqrt{10}}} + (12 \cdot 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{4+2\sqrt{2}}} + (24 \cdot 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}} + (9 \cdot 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{6+3\sqrt{2}}}.$$

Proof: We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m KB(G, x) &= \sum_{v \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(d_u+d_v)+\sqrt{d_u^2+d_v^2}}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(1+3)+\sqrt{1^2+3^2}}} + (12 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{(2+2)+\sqrt{2^2+2^2}}} \\ &+ (24 \times 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{(3+3)+\sqrt{3^2+3^2}}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{4+\sqrt{10}}} + (12 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{4+2\sqrt{2}}} \\ &+ (24 \times 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{6+3\sqrt{2}}}. \end{aligned}$$

5. CONCLUSION

We have introduced the Kepler Bhanhatti and modified Kepler Bhanhatti indices and their exponentials of a graph. Furthermore the Kepler Bhanhatti and modified Kepler Bhanhatti indices and their exponentials for two families of dendrimer nanostars are determined. Also some mathematical properties of Kepler Bhanhatti index are obtained.

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